
The Need For Consensus On The Effective Approach To Control COVID-19 Outbreak

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Abstract

Background: A recent study has discussed ways of China's success in overcoming COVID-19, presenting three concerns that occur in China that should also be addressed by each country, namely regarding emergency response measures; mobilize resources quickly; encourage people to have participated in the actions taken. Among the approaches taken by China, three ways consisting of lockdown; the willingness of people to be patient in obeying the actions taken; distancing; in our view, it is further urged to be the similar consensus adopted by each country as at least the three basic principles that required for in the strategy against the COVID-19 outbreak. Vietnam can be a representative example to discuss, understand and realize the importance of these three basic principles enough to say that it also supports them as the first country to date, to our knowledge, with all sufferers of COVID-19 successfully cured at one time, discussing what essentially has not been analyzed concerning the traditional epidemiological approach known to effectively control the transmission of an outbreak.

Main text: Vietnam has responded timely by immediately announced the state of national health emergency and implemented a partial quarantine or lockdown policy with initially only a ban on coming from and going out to China, Taiwan, Hong Kong, and Macau and the people in Vietnam, unspeakably, are patient and spread out or distanced. These actions of the Vietnamese seem to have had arguably an impact on all COVID-19 sufferers successfully cured in one time and the absence of new confirmed cases of COVID-19 infection that lasted for some time.

Conclusions: The recent study who thereafter concludes the need for global coordination in interventions and responses to the outbreak by reflecting lessons from China has demonstrated the implications supporting our view of the need for a consensus similarly by each authority regarding at least the three basic principles that required for to be performed in controlling the outbreak transmission, COVID-19, in the form of the lockdown, patience in facing outbreak situations, and distancing that all of those performed simultaneously.

INTRODUCTION

COVID-19 originated in Wuhan City, Hubei Province of China, is still a threat to people in the world. Many countries take dissimilar ways and policies to stop the spread of this already pandemic (also said as a global epidemic). Until now, deaths from COVID-19 infections have reached more than 100,000 people worldwide accompanied by its rapid increased in numbers and spread throughout the world. Qian et. al. have recapitulated the ways of China and discussed their success thereafter, as the first origin, in fighting against COVID-19 [1]. They raised that there are three concerns as occurring in China that every country similarly also to tackle, which are about the emergency response actions; mobilize resources quickly; encourage people proactively

and orderly to participate in measures undertaken. Of various acts taken as analyzed by Qian et. al., in our view, there three ways that required for at least that we argue are fundamentally needed and we encourage to be a consensus similarly performed by every authority in the strategy running to control the outbreak i.e. COVID-19 consisting of the lockdown; the willingness of people to patience to obey the acts taken; the distancing. To further discuss, understand and realize the importance of these three ways performed by China, Vietnam may become the representative instance to discuss relatively the interesting role of these three ways enough to say also supporting them as the first country to date, to our knowledge, with all COVID-19 sufferers successfully cured at one time (16 people were confirmed between 21 January 2020 and 12 February 2020, which then

all were recovered including a 73 years old patient and discharged from the hospital on 26 February 2020) [2]. Actually, the three ways as the three basic principles to control the transmission of the outbreak, in our knowledge, have been around for centuries [3, 4], in discussing to what fundamentally has not been analyzed by Qian et. al. regarding fully historical traditional epidemiological approaches that known effectively control the transmission [1] that have been similarly demonstrated, though seemingly unintentional, in the successful recovery of all those COVID-19 sufferers in Vietnam [5, 6].

DISCUSSION

The first basic principle: no in, no out

The type of lockdown or quarantine expected to control the outbreak [3, 4], from our view here, is a total quarantine or the lockdown that does not allow anyone to come in to or go out of the place of the epidemic. The Vietnamese government seems to understand the fundamental of this concept by declaring it firmly in a single statement only that there has been a national health emergency and revoking Chinese visas including stopping all flights from and to China, Taiwan, Hong Kong, and Macau which take effect immediately on 1 February 2020, not too long after the first COVID-19 case was confirmed in the country [5]. Nonetheless, the quarantine or the lockdown action carried out by the Vietnamese government is still partial according to our opinion, which in reality seems to correlate with the emergence of 15 new cases confirmed from 7 March 2020 to 9 March 2020 after quite a long time there were no confirmed infections since 13 February 2020 [2]. The majority of these new cases come from "import" cases, namely those who came into Vietnam from countries that the Vietnamese government did not prohibit at the time, for example, one from Mexico, another from Ireland, and 7 from the UK.

The second basic principle: be patient

The noble of being patient has been displayed by both the government of Vietnam with its acts constancy and consistency and people of Vietnam with their obedience when the government of Vietnam decided to quarantine a number of villages containing peasant areas inhabited by 10 thousand people that related to the COVID-19 outbreak with a period of 20 days [6]. This attitude of patience as learned for centuries [3, 4] in our view seems to have quite an impact to control the outbreak in Vietnam with very few new "local" cases emerging when compared to the "import"

cases.

The third basic principle: be spread out or distanced

The Vietnamese Government through the involvement of their army has implemented what has been evident for centuries [3, 4], in our opinion, although not intentionally through an order, that people in the peasant areas that quarantined in the COVID-19 outbreak are naturally conditioned to keep staying at their home (also known as physical or social distancing) [6].

CONCLUSIONS

The study by Qian et. al. that afterwards concluded about the need for global coordination on interventions and response to outbreaks by reflecting-lessons from China [1], as the first origin, have shown the implication as a reasonable basis implicated to what we encourage to be followed-up to be a consensus similarly by every authority regarding principle similarities at least on the three basic principles that required for to control the transmission of an outbreak, COVID-19, which all done as a whole consists of a total quarantine or the lockdown, patience on adhering the measures taken and be spread out or distanced so as not to be easily affected by outbreaks as in gathered condition. These all three must run together, as ever done during the 1918 influenza pandemic long-ago, which the WHO recently has even in line by explicitly directing each country to carry out all steps to cope with the COVID-19 outbreak by not limited to do either quarantine or social distancing only [7], which exhibited Wuhan city, China, successfully reduced drastically of COVID-19 active cases just recently as the success instance who perform all these three principles [8]. Dissimilarities on basic principles in coping the COVID-19 outbreak in the matter of people distance each other accompanied by no total (including only partial) quarantine or lockdown will lead to "import" cases keep potentially occurred and much more, coming from abroad as Vietnam ever experienced [2, 6]; total quarantine or the lockdown without people being patience to obey the steps taken will result in more "local" transmission and cases happening, as Italy onerously facing [9]; total quarantine or the lockdown accompanied by people gathered in the area will lead to the outburst of transmitted cases and even fatalities, as practised-turn out disastrous on the Diamond Princess cruise ship situation as a closed site of COVID-19 outbreak [10].

ABBREVIATIONS

COVID-19: Coronavirus disease 2019

UK: United Kingdom

WHO: World Health Organization

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